

Political Leadership Identities and Communication-Action Alignments of Selected Democratic Party Presidents

Emma Jimo (PhD)

Department of Politics & International Relations

Lead City University, Ibadan

emma.jimo@lcu.edu.ng; saintlyemmajimo@gmail.com

Abstract

Political communication is a politician's veritable tool for policy and leadership character revelations. Its importance underlies and massive government investment in public communication so that governments make calculated human capital commitment. Political leaders and communicators are or should usually be deeply rooted in, influenced, and limited by certain (un)written codes. This study examined how two democratic party presidential standard bearers, American Obama and Nigerian Obasanjo, presented whatever they said; and why they did, or not do as told. The thesis problem was mainly unravelling identifiable comparisons, and communication identities of two flag-bearers that turned executive presidents and how their presidential political communication correlated, linked, and affected the polity to which it was communicated. The paper answered two research questions: what were the politics and political communication identities of two presidents, and how much did their politics, or stipulated leadership roles align with their actual actions? Related literature was reviewed. The study fitted into two models, using two political communication theories: mainly 'Aristotelian Political Rhetoric and 'Constructivism' as theoretical guides. Using original communications of two presidents, this comparative and historical study – requiring qualitative methodology – bridged the sparse scholarship on comparative presidential leadership and political communication. Purposively selected sample population were collated, analysed and interpreted, deploying multiple instruments, majorly content and discourse analyses chosen for their effectiveness at measuring predetermined variables. Selected published presidential communication totalling 336 obtained from secondary sources formed the sample population. Main findings revealed both presidents largely differed in their communication-achievement alignment, though they had similar political background. They were more widely divergent in their communication identities in accomplishment of statutory political leadership responsibilities. The paper concludes that the presidents did less of policy actions on their talking points.

Keywords: Political Leadership, Political Communication, Identities, Democratic Party, Two Presidents

Introduction

Comparative political studies and leaders' performances are gaining grounds among political observers and scholars across geographical lines, now that technology shrinks the world and blots out geographical boundaries. This paper or researcher's focus is a 'dual-national comparative' and 'dual-personality' as he sets out to contrast two research subjects across time, space and place (that is, continents and countries), which reveals the beauty and great strengths in this kind of 'cross-national comparative research' capable of promoting the possibility of testing generalisations about politics when one political situation is juxtaposed with other similar conditions. From the viewpoint of comparativists students or scholars of comparative politics one major justification for comparative studies is their belief in the irrationality or undesirability of making reliable statements about most political situations by merely narrowly looking at one side or case.

Comparative research in political communication further enables a critical inspection and evaluation of findings from one faculty and geographical boundary, using the examination of other scholars, without borders, thereby enabling reliable conclusions with a widespread validity. To the best of this researcher's knowledge, research into communication content, style and strategies used by an American and a Nigerian president have not been addressed sufficiently before, if ever. Thus, there is justification for this arguably seemingly imbalance comparisons between Nigeria and America and their presidents, not merely for academic purposes but ultimately for problem-solving.

In most African democracies, perhaps the most demonised concept today is political leadership, often seen and labelled as the bane of societal development, such that the greatest problem is a lack of leadership or almost becoming a hackneyed expression. The Nigerian state has been led by both military adventurists, including a handful of rogue-rulers, soldiers-turned-civilians, and different categories of politicians through both good times and hard times. Nigeria was, and is still believed to be an African giant, and correctly in both geographical and human population sizes as well as in quality and quantity of its potential and actual wealth. But, Nigeria is painfully referred to as being a 'giant without gallantry'(Ottuh 2015:42). In a 2011 survey, it ranked the World's Happiest Place, but took a sharp turn to first rank as the World's 91st Happiest Country in 2018 in the 2018 World Happiness Report, then plunged further down ranking as the World's 6th Saddest in the same year in Steve Hanke's (2018:1) Misery Index and then becoming the Poverty Capital of the World in 2019 (with about 87 million persons living in extreme poverty) by the estimation of The World Poverty Clock. Nigeria is self-made victim of resource-curse, a socio-political phenomenon of being so blessed and yet poor! Thus, it seems rational to entertain an agreement with scholars like Eghosa Osaghae (2015:1) that Nigeria is still a giant but a 'crippled giant' whose post-independence politics is firmly rooted and 'deeply entrenched in its colonial history'.

Politics does not operate in isolation; it is driven by leadership, which is central to the making of the common values and interests of the people. Leadership is, therefore, an instrument worth examining in a quest for societal development.

A leading distinguished professor of political science and scholar of the presidency, Edwards III, and a renowned writer and lecturer on American president and presidency, Wayne (2014:15), identify at least four approaches to studying presidencies named 'legal, institutional, political power, and psychological'. The institutional approach examines the presidency as an institution, while the political power approach focuses on 'the people within' the institution and 'their relationship' with other humans with a view to explaining 'behaviour' and 'making generalisation about it'. More importantly, the psychological approach seeks to explain the reasons or motives behind the president's behaviour and also looks into the 'external factors', including and more importantly 'the media.'

Conceptual Review

A number of concepts are reviewed and illuminated to provide intellectual enhancement, expand perspectives of the paper, as well as accommodate and critique previous endeavours on the concepts, ultimately leading to identifying the gap the paper seeks to fill.

Leadership

Leadership, like political communication, is apparently not yet a very famous faculty in the Nigeria knowledge industry but the leadership question and its societal development implications, challenges and potentials are more imperative now than previously. In 1983, one of Nigeria's finest writers ever, Chinua Achebe, published. "*The Trouble with Nigeria,*" identifying, ahead of other problems, 'failure of leadership,' including a 'lack of intellectual rigour or depth in Nigerian leadership style' as a bane of development. The verdict of the writer is that 'there is nothing wrong with the Nigerian character,' but the 'trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a failure of leadership'(Teilanyo, 2017:42).

The leadership question, agitation, or concern is still a current challenge in the polity, more than three-and-a-half decades after Achebe's work or more than half a century after independence, which is worrisome to some scholars and citizens. There is no known one most acceptable description or definition of the concept. What is widely known to literature is that the diversity of definitions enables different definers and scholars focus on a specific component of leadership as a concept. W.G. Bennis considers leadership as 'the process by which an agent induces a subordinate to behave in a desired manner' (Hughes, Ginnett and Curphy, 2019:4). This emphasises the top-bottom relational perspective and interactions between a leader and the led or the follower. This is one of the most frequently held notions about leadership. Leadership, therefore, is one person or entity influencing many, or training them to trail.

Fielder (2019:4) looks at leadership from the management-related standpoint of leaders directing and coordinating the work of group members. Fielder's position seems to equate manager with leader, which has been proven or debunked to not be exactly the same. His view equally relegates emotionalism, a pervasive in-built trait of humans. Fielder's view can be summed as leadership being one giving direction and coordination to actions of others. Differently, R.K. Merton (2019:4) looks at leadership from what can be labelled a 'willing will-submission angle,' saying that the concept is an interpersonal relation in which others comply, 'because they want to, not because they have to'. This contradicts the notion and a definition of government (by an Anonymous writer) as 'a group of people that makes (or forces) us do what we don't want to do'.

Leadership is thus the lure that pulls many to one. Merton thinks leadership is not or should not be imposed, rationalising that 'coercion' is not an emphasised 'leadership tool,' but of course, it is known that leadership structures imposes compliance on and compels action from followers. The duo of C.F. Roach and O. Behling (2019:4) defines leadership from a functional perspective, spelling out the term as the process of influencing an organised group toward accomplishing its goals. Their perspectives agree with John Maxwell's who says 'Everything rises and falls on leadership.'

Devito (2015:251) toes the same line of thought, defining leadership in two very different ways in research and theory. 'Leadership is the process of influencing thoughts, feelings, and behaviours of group members and establishing the direction that others follow.' He further brands leadership and influence as 'parts of the same skill' while considering leadership as 'the process of empowering others' and conceiving a leader as 'the person who helps others maximise their potential and to take control of their lives'. These two definitions are not mutually exclusive; in fact, most effective leaders do both; they influence and they empower. Leroy Eimes (2019:1) similarly sees a leader as the one 'who sees more than others see, who sees farther than others see, and who sees before others see'. His argument is that great lessons on how to be an extraordinary leader can emerge from observing very poor leaders and learning from their blunders and those of others. Nevidjon's (2019:1) view captures leadership succinctly, describing it as 'making ordinary people do extraordinary things'.

Therefore, leadership is making; it is one making others do. It is acting. It is recreating desirable extraordinariness from 'ordinary.' In Gary Burnison's (2016:21) calculation, leadership is the competence to recruit, attract, and compensate people; provide a moral compass; match their skill sets to different needs in the organisation that I'm running, whether it's a company or a government; and then to make sure that they work collaboratively and collectively. He aligns, saying that leadership is a journey with others and all about others and their achievement such that there is no leadership without followership (2021: 21). This view agrees to Martin Luther King Jr's view that what is very important is that a leader must be a 'learner.'

John Maxwell (2021:21) advises that a leader builds a 'relational bridge' between himself and the people he leads. He believes that, 'to lead yourself, (you have to) use your head; to lead

others, use your heart'. So, it can be concluded 'leadership is an empathy business.' Thus, leadership is building.

Besides the debatable place of formal education in political leadership, some scholars consider skill, communication prowess, intellect, and several other qualities as germane. D.P. Campbell's definition is from the viewpoint of man as a creative entity, such that he considers leadership as creating conditions for a team to be effective. Both of them agree to the assertion that 'leadership is a creative enterprise' as this researcher conceives it. Effectiveness is often a criterion for determining the viability and acceptability of a leader or leadership echelon.

The next definition has its root in the preceding notion, as R. Horgan, G. Curphy, R.B. Kaiser, and T. Chamorro-Premuzic (2019:4) align partly with Campbell and Ginnett, defining 'the how' and 'the what' of the ability to encourage employees ... build teams ... and achieve results. Consequently, leadership is a cost-effective problem-solving instrument.

The core concern of Munroe's (2019) *The Power of Character in Leadership* ... is (lack of) moral force or 'crisis of character' in leaders. He posits in the preface that leadership is a 'central' phenomenon in human society, without which 'nothing happens, succeeds, develops, advances, improves, is altered or transformed, or is corrected.' His contention or assertion is that 'character' is 'an essential element of leadership.' From this researcher's view, this concept can be represented diagrammatically for simplification and greater clarity as follows.

Fig 1: Leadership Squares of Influence

Source: The Researcher's Construct, 2019

There are four cardinal angles a, b, c, and d, each representing a key phenomenon in the leadership intermixes. The centrality of leadership is stressed, serving as the nerve centre of both human (follower and leader) and material (situation and society) elements of intermixes. Each square represents a geographical space in a society; let's say a county, ward, local government area, or a state. The squares are similar, regardless of the size of the geographical space leadership affects. Each square is dependent on another, or at least connected to others, even if independent politically, geographically or structurally. That is, each square does not exist in isolation, and

then all squares are interdependent and interacting practically. Each has similar human and material resources, at the centre of which leadership actively occupies, and productively manipulating the four cardinal factors (a, b, c, and d) for utilitarian outcomes.

The Nigerian state has had both military and executive presidents since independence, but it is researchable or debatable if Nigeria ever had 'leaders!' Some thinkers, perhaps political escapists say and promote the notion that 'governments have no business in business.' The researcher raises a curious question: Could Nigeria have been greater or worse if treated as a 'business'? Possibly, but what is almost always certain is that 'government is by no means a mean business,' so much, that it is arguably, in the researcher's view 'a dodgy fallacy, fraudulent bulk-passing, rebranded falsehood, repackaged lie, and hypocritical avoidance' that government doesn't have business in/with business. Rather, this notion itself seems to express an indication of dearth of 'executive leadership,' knowing that in reality 'government itself is the single biggest business of any society or a people.' In Nigeria, for instance, there is no business that binds its over 200 million people, as the government does. No other business has this wide coverage, patronage or concerns.

The idea is that for as long as money is involved in running a government, it is a serious business. Wherever money is, there is business! The logic, far beyond hypothesizing, is that everything that is involved in running a business is involved in running government, namely manpower, money, machine and equipment, materials, information and energy; therefore, it can be asserted that government is a big business. The reason a society is retarded is traceable to the fact that those running the government are running at a loss. If a government runs at a loss, it means running everyone and everything down! This is to further strengthen the point that being accountable in leadership is similarly germane.

Major changes are needed to survive effectively in this changing environment. Great leadership is, therefore, needed to cope with rapid change. Leadership is concerned with setting direction, aligning with people, and providing motivation, by inspiring or stirring in them some sense of belonging and self-esteem, touching them at their innermost and deepest level. This is why Maxwell concludes 'leadership is an empathy business.'

Like several other scholars, Hans J. Morgenthau, - Professor at the University of Chicago and Author of *Politics Among Nations: The Struggle for Power and Peace*, first published in 1948 believes that 'vision of thoughtful political leadership' is a tool for solving some political problems. He aligns with and emphasises Weberian notion of charismatic leadership. The Weberian political leadership school of thought awards a charismatic leader 'the power to produce the important change' (Neacsu, 2010:97).

The development of the Nigerian society is being frequently challenged by some political and leadership realities in Nigeria, such as ballot looting, under-aged voting, multiple voting, overestimated votes, manipulation of electoral umpire, summation distortion, prolonged post-

election litigations, recycled politicians syndrome, impunity, growing lack of equity and fairness, zero welfare packages for the majority, penury for the vulnerable, and (consequently) dearth of a leadership model. This long list of national socio-political issues is what the Nigeria's new leadership structure must upturn in order to be considered an effective leadership syndicate.

Theoretical Framework

From diverse faculties, over time, models and frameworks have been evolved to amplify and explain political communication and their implications for studying the concept. Some are contextually not directly related to the kernel of this thesis. The 'agenda setting,' 'social responsibility,' 'libertarian,' and 'authoritarian' theories are four of the most popular and most frequently used.

However, the study adopts two of them for their greater capacity for amplifying and simplifying the research(er)'s focus.

The first is Aristotle's Aristotelian Political Rhetoric. Aristotle's Rhetorics, written some 2,300 years ago in ancient Greece, was one of the earliest systematic studies of public speaking. It was in this work that the three kinds of persuasive appeals – logos (or logical proof), pathos (emotional appeals), and ethos (appeals based on the character of the speaker) – were introduced. This three-part division is still followed today (James 2019:1). Rhetorics, Aristotle-made tool for 'practical debate,' a treatise on the 'art of persuasion,' is believed to have been written in the fourth century B.C. and is a system of persuasion based on knowledge instead of upon manipulation and omission.'

Larter (2017:1) reiterates that as a foremost ancient Greek great thinker in political communication, and in many other fields of study, Aristotle believes that the fundamental purpose or aim of communication is persuasion, which he also thinks can be achieved by three means, tagged 'forms of proof' in Aristotelian rhetoric, namely 'logos, ethos, and pathos.' McCormick (2014:131) says logos is plausible and rational arguments or messages; ethos is the communicator's credibility or moral standing, by being intelligent, truthful and rationally emotional or being capable of emotion management, and then pathos which is having understanding of the nature and composition of the speaker's audience.

The study is carried out within the scope of Lasswell's, and Newcomb's Symmetry model contrived in 1953 by Theodore Newcomb. Harold Lasswell developed the Lasswell Model, primarily a verbal model, in 1948. The model presupposes that while studying or examining the meaning of communication, a number of questions such as 'Who (the communicator)? Says or sends what (message)? By which means or channel (is the message sent)? To whom (is the message sent or who is the receiver)? With what effect (what is the outcome?)(Wroblewski, 2018:1). These questions must be answered, and appropriately too.

The second one is Newcomb's Symmetry Model. Newcomb's is an interactional model concerned with 'intentional' asymmetrical, bi-directional or symbiotic communication – an exchange between two persons. It makes up for the linear nature of the Lasswell's, explaining how a message source relays his message to a 'receiver' such that he executes an action, and injects a feedback on the basis of what is heard or received.

The second theory is an international politics theory named 'constructivism' that Hastedt and Felice describe as being capable of focusing on and highlighting 'contextual analysis' and the conceptual 'meaning of events and ideas' in relation to the environment in which they occur. Constructivism focuses on how interests behind certain policies become decisions ultimately. Thus, constructivism is a theory that explains the transmutation of lofty ideals to a workable idea that benefits the society.

Methods

The researcher raises a couple of simple research questions based on Harold Lasswell's Model questions, popularly referred to as 'Wh-questions': who, what, what channel, for whom and to what effect? The research questions formulated to guide this study are as follows:

1. What were the politics and political identities in communications of Barack Obama and Olusegun Obasanjo?
2. How much did Barack Obama's and Olusegun Obasanjo's politics, policies or stipulated leadership responsibilities align with their activated communications? Two corresponding objectives – main and specific – were constructed for answering. The researcher focused on alignment between the leaders' politics, or communications and achievements. This was a communication fidelity test.

The time scope of the study is altogether 16 years, four-year of four terms, 1999-2007, Obasanjo's two four-year terms, and 2007-2015, Barack Obama's two-terms. The spatial or geographical scope, alternatively called the delineation of the study is primarily the United States, and Nigeria, further streamlined to both American and Nigerian politics, or more specifically, presidencies, including their information dissemination and public communication systems.

The instrument scope of the survey is primarily content or textual analysis, together with discourse analysis and case study, all chosen on account of their empirically proven capacity for providing research direction or solution to the predetermined concepts or problem, and based on previous researchers' consistent use of same tools to solve similar research problems, such that this researcher does not have to reinvent the wheel. The sample or participants are drawn from all published communications of the presidents that are available and accessible. A potent justification for the scope limits is that studies of the exact title, nature, goal or focus, or dominant subject are not known to have been done previously.

Findings and Discussions

Findings are as enumerated, explained, exemplified and/or tabulated below. The researcher found the following specifiable identities of the presidents, first, in Barack Obama's communication, as follows: serial reiteration as a repeated concern, amplification of economic woes cum economy-related concerns, America's global leadership position and role, political dichotomy management, presidential communication of achievement by repetition, and repeated demonisation of political adversary. One of these is exemplarily expatiated hereunder.

Repeated Demonisation of Political Adversary

A constant factor or picture in Obama's communication was 'victim demonisation', a mechanism Obama deployed at will to paint gory pictures of a potential target in order to sufficiently create convincing reasons to attack and take out the target.

For another instance, he said or admitted the 'fight in Syria' was both 'a civil war' and 'a proxy war.' Obama used demonisation of the adversary as a political weapon, and communication tool or strategy, as well as justification for his action against the Libyan state. In his March 2011 address to America on Libya in Washington D.C., he reeled out more than twenty (20) sins of Muammer Qaddafi. Obama called Muammer Qaddafi 'a tyrant' who ruled Libya for 'four decades,' denying his people freedom. He labelled him an exploiter, a murderer, who 'murdered opponents,' a terrorist, who terrorised innocent people – including Americans, a genocide perpetrator, who hanged civilians, and killed over a thousand people in a single day, among other demonisation insignias. In June 2011 at a press conference in White House, he reinforced his demeaning communication declaring 'a guy who was a state sponsor of terrorist against the United States of America is pinned down, and the noose is tightening around him,' to hasten processes leading to Qaddafi's end. Amazingly, the list seems vindictively endless! The length of the list was meant to create some piled-up and bottled-up effects of the negatives. Then, Obama filed a list over 16 actions against Muammer Qaddafi's Libya. On one occasion, when he was questioned, he ruled out ever reconciliation with Qaddafi, bluntly and hastily judging that 'He (Qaddafi) needs to go.' This was foreshadowing his death, beyond expecting his stepping down, since a 'noose is around his neck.'

In September 2011, while addressing United Nations General Assembly, Obama regarded 2011 as a remarkable year because 'the Qaddafi regime is over. Gbagbo, Ben Ali, (sic) Mubarak are no longer in power, Osama bin Laden is gone....' Apparently, this was gloating over enemies' misfortunes inflicted partly by Obama's America.

Findings

The presidents' stipulated political leadership roles are assessed as indicated in the table below.

Table 1: Presidential Political Leadership Responsibility Commitment and Activated Communication Alignment

S NO.	Responsibilities	Most Likely Rating based on Obama’s Communication	Most Likely Rating based on Obasanjo’s Communication
1.	Head of State	Frequently so	Frequently so
2.	Head of Government	Frequently so	Frequently so
3.	Commander-in-Chief	Frequently so	Frequently so
4.	Chief Executive	Frequently so	Frequently so
5.	Agenda setter	Seldom	Seldom
6.	Foreign Policymaker	Often	Often
7.	Economic leader	Often	Often
8.	Moral Leader	Often	Seldom
9.	Crisis manager	Often	Seldom
10.	Party Leader	Prominently so	Seldom

Source: Researcher's construct, 2020

The next table indicates of a cross-section of what presidents talked about, reflecting their preferences or political communication concerns.

Table 2 Classification by Discourse or Major Thematic Concern

S/NO.	Major Classification of Communication by Theme	Minimum Number of times
1.	Government Feedback and Governance	23
2.	Religion	4
3.	Economy and Economics	23
4.	Health	9
5	Education	5
6.	(In)security, Terrorism & Nuclear Weapons	19
7.	Gun Control & Gun Violence	4
8.	Military and Intelligence	12
9.	Art, Artefact and Historical	3
10.	Disaster & Man-made Tragedy	17
11.	Politics & Political Controversy	14
12.	Diplomacy/International Affairs	17
13.	Immigration	3
14.	Eulogy and Human Resource Appreciation	25
15	Diverse Issues	4

Source: Researcher's Construct, 2020

The third table clarifies the sample broad categorisation of verbal presidential political communication.

Table 3: Communication Classification by Nature of Content

S.No	Broad Categorisation by Nature	Minimum Number of time
1.	Tributes	4
2.	Q & A/Interview/Press Conference & Briefing	28
3.	State of the Nation Address	4
4.	Response to Tragedy	10
5.	Announcement	3
6.	Press statement	3
7.	Address and Speech	93
8.	Remembrance and Memorial	9
9.	Campaign and Debate	3
10.	Victory Speech/Inaugural/Farewell	7
11.	Candidacy/Nomination Address	7
12.	Remarks	12

Source: Researcher's Construct, 2020

Obama Speech-Policy Attainment Evaluation

One of Obama's most talked-about policies or government focuses was his Health Care Act, or Affordable Health Care programme. As a presidential candidate, he idealised or opinionised that '... I want to stop talking about the outrage of 47 million Americans without health care and start actually doing something about it.' February, 2010, Obama expressed displeasure with irrational indebtedness, saying: '... it would be a terrible mistake to borrow against our children's future to pay our way today ...' In June 2010, at Pittsburgh, while addressing America's economy, he again brought America's indebtedness to limelight. 'This new foundation is based on reforms that will make ... our government less burdened with debt.' Apparently, Obama, like Obasanjo, had concerns for low or zero indebtedness. However, in the days of Obama, America remained one of world's top-five most heavily indebted developed nations, and has been so since then. Therefore Obama's communication did not match policy actions in this regard.

The need or necessity for national unity was repeated several times in Obama's communication. The call for unity arguably stemmed from his personal first-hand experience as a product of a

broken home. He knew first-hand that divisiveness slowed progress and threw a nation into turmoil, so he reiterated 'We are not a collection of red states and blue states. We are the United States of America.' In the address to his supporters in Des Moines, Iowa, in 2008, he reiterated the uniting tendencies of Americans, whom he commended, saying, 'you came together ... democrats, Republicans, and Independents, to stand up and say that we are one nation. We are one people.' He arrived at a similar conclusion as Martin Luther King, that 'unity is how we (America) shall overcome.' This came with, or revealed a great measure of nationalism and patriotism.

Obama's speech-policy attainment can also be evaluated looking at the reiteration of economic woes that he frequently engaged in. A major talking point for Obama was what looked to him like his country's economic woes.

Even while talking about spirituality, he resorted to castigating previous regimes by saying, 'unemployment is at its level in more than a quarter of a century. Nowhere is it higher than the African American community. Poverty is on the rise.' The lamentational piece appeared to have been an unmistakable concern that emerged in his presidential communication.

In April 2010, in the address on Reforming Wall Street, Obama stated categorically, however debatable, that 'More than 8 million people have lost their jobs.' In April 2010, at Cooper Union, he again reemphasised America 'losing an average of 750,000 jobs each month.'

Threats to national interest and security were altogether an index for evaluating his policy attainment. Further, at the ACA Impact Speech and Question and Answer session in San Jose, California June 7, 2013, Obama referred to 'two commitments,' two most important commitments he made 'to keep the American people safe' and 'to uphold the constitution'. He ended up working in that direction, ensuring that he took out a world's most wanted and deadliest terrorist in his days in office, Osama bin Laden.

Obasanjo's Communication Foci or Talking Points

Four major themes formed the fulcrum of Obasanjo's speech, with indebtedness and debt cancellation taking the lead. By far, the most prevalent theme in Obasanjo's communication was debt, national indebtedness, or cancellation of debt. During his visit to France in February 2000, arguably for the purpose of influencing cancellation of Nigeria's debts to the Paris Club, he commented on what made his address imperative, which was 'a mention of Nigeria's indebtedness to the Paris Club' a sum of US\$26 billion. He traced the history of the \$26 billion debt from the initial \$3.5 billion in 1980 to the compound sum of \$5.8 billion in 1985 to \$26 billion. He appealed to logic, albeit financial or economic logic, to drive home his point. He argued that there was no business or project worth \$3.5 billion 'that would yield so much' as \$21 billion profit in only 18 years, and therefore, concluded or alluded to the unfairness of international borrowing by developing countries such as Nigeria. As far as indebtedness was concerned, for Obasanjo,

reiteration was a viable communication tool in order to achieve a goal. The economy and corruption also attracted his communication concerns. He stated it in a February 2000 speech that a 'major priority of our Government (sic) is the economy.' At the occasion of formal signing of the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act in June 2000, Obasanjo identified corruption as 'an enemy of development ... a cankerworm, the antithesis of development and progress' which 'invariably strangles the system' He referred to corruption as 'the twin brother of inefficiency' in his January 2000 speech.

Obasanjo Speech-Policy Attainment Evaluation

The researcher further reconciled what President Olusegun Obasanjo had said with what he did eventually. The goal was to further show the achievement of the content of communication, and test for fidelity of his communication, with a view to ascertaining whether he was politicking, merely politically correct, or being practically a responsible political communicator. He must have talked about certain themes of major concerns, including making plans or promises to do certain things. A clear demonstration of leadership or accomplishment of leadership responsibilities was tracking to find fulfilled promises or accomplished policies.

A notable concern of Obasanjo's administration was the desire or so-called 'commitment to combating poverty ...' Although he admitted also it was not a quick fix, or 'a one-day affair' but in spite of 'additional budget ... made available to kick-start the poverty eradication programme' he mentioned in his 1st January 2000 speech, close to two decades after, Nigeria was the poverty capital of the world (arguably though) such that it looked mere unattainable to do what he communicated to his constituents, that is, to build a Nigeria where no citizen should lack the basics of life – food, shelter, education, employment and health care ...' Even from an economic point of view, he spoke about health being wealth, theorizing that health is 'the wealth of a nation: primary health care.'

In a press statement by Obasanjo on the issue of power supply, March 2000, he promised to restore 'sanity to power supply to the country' asserting categorically his 'word' would be his 'bond' and he would use 'everything within' his power to deliver 'with NEPA' by the grace of God and also in line with his 'taking oath of office.' It turned out that in spite of almost swearing by God, NEPA, (which has now changed names twice, first to PHCN, then GENCO and DISCO) was not yet in 'a suitable shape and condition for privatisation and in fact, has been experiencing troublesome, oppressive, and shady private ownership almost twenty years after. This was one of his promises cum attainment discrepancies.

In the same month, March 2000, in one of his speeches, Obasanjo himself pronounced a verdict 'NEPA has failed, and failed woefully.' Up to now, the verdict has not changed, in spite of his renewing 'our resolve to put an end to it.' Nigeria, with an estimated population of 206 million in 2021, still relies on 15,000 megawatts of electricity. It was the lowest point in Obasanjo's

communication infidelity and policy action. This clearly negated his philosophy or at least, belief about fidelity in political communication, revealed in his own words, 'Government should not say something and do something else. For as long as you do that government will become a laughing stock.'

There was, therefore, practically a lingering lacuna in the Obasanjo speech-policy attainment scale. A major reason is attributable to the failure of ICPC Act to terminate corruption in Nigeria's public space.

Obasanjo communicated assurances that Nigeria's refineries would 'be fully operational' by the end of year 2000 and deregulation would 'tame the monster of fuel scarcity' but about twenty years after, not only that NNPC still did 'massive importation' - despite having three refineries that were obviously or suspiciously moribund - as in the days of Obasanjo, but fuel scarcity still persisted just like 'the cyclical crises associated with increases in prices of petroleum products.' He gave a false hope and miscommunicated that part deregulation by 'removal of subsidy' was the 'best solution' to the oil sector. Fair enough, he had on one occasion of national broadcast bluntly stated that importation was inevitable: 'Even if all our refineries are (sic) working to full capacity as if they were installed today, we will still need to import 12 million litres of product everyday' (sic). About 20 years after, the oil sector was still badly affected by subsidy scandal in all successive administrations. In March, 2000, he amplified an achievement of his administration which was regaining 'the confidence of the international Investment Community.' This was a credible statement as Obasanjo administration did not only attract investors such as in the mobile telecommunication industry, but Obasanjo emerged Nigeria's most widely accepted and officially travelled president both in and out of office. Again, speech-attainment evaluation or discourse analysis gave opportunity of assessing achievement of the president and his government or administration in relation to his communication.

Conclusion

Having answered research questions raised by the paper, sifted views, opinions and findings, the research(er) concludes as follows. First, findings reinforce the hypothetical assertions that there existed similitudes, correlations, variances or points of divergence between Barack Obama and Olusegun Obasanjo in leadership, politics, or communications.

Political leadership and leaders' actions were largely driven by what they frequently communicated. Communication was heavy around matters they wished and wanted to attain. When this did not happen, it indicated leadership negligence. There is a clear nexus between (understanding) leadership and the performance of statutory political responsibilities. Both presidents were similar in the aspect of making their communication central to their politics and policies.

The constituents or citizens deserve and should demand more communication engagements with their presidents, as nothing should be more important in a democracy than the people and the interest of the people. Political communication should be a legitimate responsibility of Presidents and a criterion for measuring effective political leadership. Citizens should be engaged more with conventional letter writing, which is still being taught in school as a means of communication or dissemination of information with their president. Calling for a compulsory citizen-president engagement by all means possible will make the president and presidency much more responsible to the citizens and also promote president-constituent interactionism.

Furthering the research identities rigid protocols as a limiting factor in presidential communication confining leaders to certain activities. On one occasion, Obama complained the State Service would not let him test drive a car more than a few metres, although he would have loved to test drive indeed. Therefore, presidential protocol should be tempered with reasonable presidential freedom such that protocol will no longer make a stranger of a president among the people he should serve.

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